

MELISSOPALYNOLOGICAL STUDIES IN INDIA: A REVIEW

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Abstract- Melissopalynology is the study of pollen grains in honey. It helps to assess the bee foraging preference of the region by providing the exact information regarding the floral resource to bees. Floral calendar of the concerned area of study can be easily prepared by melissopalynological studies. In the present review, an attempt has been made to assess the work done in India which started in early fifties. Present communication also gives an insight to different plants preferred by honey bees. The present review is also exploring current status and scope in this research area which can help in improving the present situation of honey market in India.

Key words: Honey, melissopalynology, pollen, bee foraging.

INTRODUCTION

Honey, popularly known as golden liquid, is a natural sweetener that is produced by honey bees by collecting nectar from flowers. From centuries, honey has been consumed as food (Zumla and Lulat, 1990). Honey is a natural product of very high nutritive value which is made when the nectar (floral) and sweet deposits from plants (non-floral) are gathered, modified and stored in the honeycombs by honeybees (Manyi-Lohet *et al.*, 2011)

Pollen grains are essential food for honey bees as they are source of proteins, vitamins, minerals and fatty substances (Gary, 1975). They are an important tool in analysing honey. For identifying floral nectar sources utilized by honey bees to produce honey, different pollen grains from different plants are used. This helps in labelling of major and minor nectar sources of honey sample (Sadia Bibi *et al.*, 2008). For understanding bee foraging preferences of honey bees, it is essentially important to have the basic understanding of the local flora. Most easy and simplest method widely followed by majority of botanists to do so is by performing melissopalynological studies of the honey samples collected from the desired area.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of pollen content of honey is melissopalynology (= melittopalynology). This term comes from the Greek words for “bee” and “honey” along with the word for “study of dust,” now referred to “pollen”. Such studies are beneficial in determination of the floral content and origin of honey samples present in a particular geographical area during different seasons. (Parades *et al.*, 2020). This method is recognized worldwide as being the least expensive and quickest way to determine the pollen content of honey. Concentration of representative floral pollen in honey is dependent upon several factors such as: structure of flower; size and shape of pollen grains; and how long it spends in the bee’s honey stomach.

Melissopalynological studies have been used to verify honey types produced from floral sources that are “under represented” or “over represented” in the relative pollen counts of the honey samples. Verification of preferred (premium) types of honey is often difficult because many of them come from plant sources that are either weak pollen producers or have pollen that is under-represented in honey (Bryant & Jones, 2001).

Apis dorsata, *Apis cerana* and *Apis mellifera* are the major bee species largely responsible for nectar collection in India (Chauhan *et al.* 2017), though *Apis cerana indica* is most common and utilized in bee keeping apiaries. Study of pollen grains in honey samples helps in identifying the purity of honey. Presence or absence of different pollen types helps in identifying the main plant sources for nectar which in turn can help the native people to encourage apiculture at a larger scale and thereby generating employment opportunities to locals.

During the last few decades, analysis of pollen using honey samples have been reported from districts of Lucknow (Chaturvedi, 2009, Chauhan *et al.*, 2013), Western Himalayan Region of Uttar Pradesh (Chaturvedi, 2004), Adikmet area, Hyderabad (Kalpana *et al.*, 1990), Prakasam, Andhra Pradesh (Jhansi *et al.*, 1991, 1994), South Indian Western Ghats (Balachandra, 1999), North Eastern hill region (Singh, 1999), Karnataka (Sivaram, 2001), Maharashtra (Bhusari, 2005), Upper Gangetic Region of India (Datta *et al.*, 2008), Nilgiri Biosphere (Sivaram, 2012), Nadia, West Bengal (Bhattacharya, 2014), Tropical South India (Ponnuchanney *et al.*, 2014), Chandrapur, Maharashtra (Lakshmikant *et al.*, 2014, Borkar *et al.*, 2016), Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh (Sahney *et al.*, 2016), Vindhya Pratishthan Campus, Baramati, Pune (Harugade *et al.*, 2016), Chandrapur District, Maharashtra (Borkar and Mate., 2013), Assam (Tripathi, 2017), Kangra, Himachal Pradesh (Saklani, 2017), Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2018), Newasa tehsil, Maharashtra (Dhawan *et al.*, 2018), Nilambar Taluk, Malappuram, Kerala (Divakaran *et al.*, 2019), Dakshina Kannada Karnataka (Krishna and Patil, 2019), Paderu Vishakhapatnam Andhra Pradesh (Devender *et al.*, 2020), Eastern dry zone Karnataka (Kumar, 2020). In the present review work an attempt has been made to sum up the melissopalynological studies by different investigators in different places of India.

History

Author	Area of Study	Dominant Plant Families	Dominant Plant taxa	Economic Uses
Chaturvedi, 2009	Banthra, Lucknow, India	Fabaceae Xanthorrhoeaceae Fabaceae Amaranthaceae Rosaceae Compositae Rutaceae Linaceae Meliaceae Areaceae	<i>Cassia abbreviate</i> Oliv. <i>Asphodelusacaulis</i> Desp. <i>Pisumabyssinium</i> A. Braun <i>Chenopodiumacerifolium</i> Andr. <i>Rosa abretina</i> Gren. Ex. H. Christ <i>Carthamusarborescens</i> L. <i>Citrus assemensis</i> R.M. Dutta & Bhattacharya <i>Linumacerticarpum</i> C.M. Rogers <i>Melia azedarach</i> L. <i>Borassusaethiopicum</i> Mart.	-----
Chauhan <i>et al.</i> , 2013	Lucknow	Myrtaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae Myrtaceae Sapotaceae Fabaceae Moringaceae Moraceae	<i>Syzigium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels <i>Prosopisjuliflora</i> (Sw.) DC. <i>Prosopisspicigera</i> (L.) <i>Eucalyptus abdita</i> Brooker & Hopper <i>Madhuca indica</i> J.F. Gmel. <i>Pithecellobiumdulce</i> (Roxn.) Benth. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam. <i>Morus alba</i> L.	-----
Chaturvedi, 1989	Western Himalayan Region of Uttar Pradesh	Brassicaceae Rosaceae Betulaceae Polygonaceae	<i>Brassicaaucherii</i> Boiss <i>Prunus africana</i> (Hook. f.) <i>Alnusacuminata</i> Kunth. <i>Rumexabyssinicus</i> Jacq.	-----

Kalpana et al., 1990	Adikmet area, Hyderabad	Anacardiaceae Compositae Arecaceae Arecaceae Meliaceae Amaranthaceae Acanthaceae Rubiaceae Convolvulaceae Zygophyllaceae Lamiaceae Simaroubaceae Compositae Fabaceae Boraginaceae Fabaceae Rutaceae Myrtaceae Nyctaginaceae Rubiaceae Malvaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L. <i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L. <i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb. <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. <i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss. <i>Allmania nodiflora</i> (L.) <i>Rungia repens</i> (L.)Nees. <i>Oldenlandia umbellata</i> L. <i>Evolvulus sinoides</i> (L.)L. <i>Peltophorum ferrugineum</i> (Decne.)Benth. <i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L. <i>Ocimum americanum</i> L. <i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb. <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (L.)L. <i>Acacia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.)Willd. <i>Heliotropium zeylanicum</i> (B urm.f.)Lam. <i>Bauhinia variegata</i> L. <i>Citrus limon</i> (L.) Osbeck. <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill. <i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i> Brandege e <i>Randia diometorem</i> (Retz.) Lam. <i>Bombax malabaricum</i> DC.	-----
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Jhansi <i>et al.</i> , 1991	Prakasam, Andhra Pradesh	Fabaceae Combretaceae Fabaceae Rutaceae Lythraceae Loganiaceae Rhamnaceae Phyllanthaceae Meliaceae Myrtaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L. <i>Terminalia alata</i> Wall. <i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam. <i>Feronia elephantum</i> Correa <i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Roxb. <i>Strychnos potatorum</i> L.f. <i>Zizyphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd. <i>Phyllanthus acaciodes</i> Urb. <i>Soymida febrifuga</i> (Roxb.) A. Juss. <i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels <i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> Roxb. <i>Caesalpinia bonduie</i> (L.) Roxb.	-----
Jhansi <i>et al.</i> , 1994	Andhra Pradesh	Lythraceae Fabaceae Sapindaceae Arecaceae Acanthaceae Cucurbitaceae Verbenaceae Cucurbitaceae	<i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Roxb. <i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L. <i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Men. <i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L. <i>Hygrophila acinos</i> Heine <i>Cucumis aculeatus</i> Cogn. <i>Phyllanthus nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene <i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	-----

Singh, 1999	North Eastern Hill Region	Acanthaceae Compositae Brassicaceae Ranunculaceae Compositae Rubiaceae Solanaceae Rubiaceae	<i>Adhatodadensifora</i> Manning <i>Ageratum albidum</i> (DC.) Hemsl. <i>Brassica brachyloma</i> Boiss. &Reut. <i>Clematis acerifolia</i> Maxim <i>Helianthus agrestis</i> Pollard <i>Mussaendaacuminata</i> Blume <i>Solanumtubersum</i> L. <i>Wendlandia aberrans</i> F.C. How	Source of pollen, nectar in North Eastern Region
Bhusari, 2005	Maharashtra	Compositae Compositae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i> Cav. <i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Region selected for the investigation has good potential for sustaining beekeeping ventures because of the diversity of nectar and pollen taxa.
Datta <i>et al.</i> , 2008	Upper Gangetic region of India	Brassicaceae Apiaceae Myrtaceae Myrtaceae Polygonaceae Compositae	<i>Brassica carinata</i> A.Braun <i>Coriandrumsativum</i> L. <i>Eucalyptus accedens</i> W. Fitzg. <i>Callistemonacuminatus</i> Che el. <i>Myricaadenophora</i> Hance <i>Rumexabyssinicus</i> Jacq. <i>Erigeronabajoensis</i> Cronquist	Plants useful for apiculture in these regions.

Sivaram,2012	Nilgiri Biosphere	Fabaceae Arecaceae Rubiaceae Malvaceae Euphorbiaceae Araliaceae Sapindaceae Fabaceae Rubiaceae Acanthaceae	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub. <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. <i>Coffea arabica</i> J.F. Leroy <i>Bombax albidum</i> Gagneb. <i>Croton abegii</i> Urb. & Ekman <i>Schefflera</i> <i>acaropunctata</i> Frodin <i>Sapindus marginatus</i> Vahl <i>Bauhinia aculeata</i> L. <i>Mussaenda acuminata</i> Blume <i>Justicia simplex</i> D. Don	Honeybees are important in terms of pollination of various economically important crops and also to increase farm income through honey and other hive products like pollen, wax, royal jelly and propolis. Pollen analysis in honey of different regions provides information on sources and quality of honey yielding plants.
Chauhan et al., 2013	Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh	Fabaceae Menispermaceae Moringaceae Amaranthaceae	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth. <i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Wild.) Miers. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam. <i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	-----
Bhattacharya, 2014	Nadia, West Bengal	Compositae	<i>Parthenium argentatum</i> A. Gray	-----
Ponnuchamy et al., 2014	Tropical South India	Anacardiaceae Arecaceae Arecaceae Arecaceae	<i>Lannea acida</i> A. Rich <i>Phoenix acaulis</i> Roxb. <i>Borassus aethiopicum</i> Mart. <i>Cocos acaulis</i> Drude	-----
Laxmikant et al., 2014	Chandrapur, Maharashtra	Fabaceae Asteraceae Lamiaceae Capparidaceae Solanaceae	<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Millsp. <i>Celosia argentea</i> L. <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (Sw.) DC <i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit. <i>Capparis grandis</i> L.f. <i>Cleome gynandra</i> L. <i>Capsicum annuum</i> L. <i>Dodonea viscosa</i> (L.) Jacq.	All these taxa constitute important pollen source during the summer season for the honey bees of this forest area.

Borkar <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Chandrapur , Maharashtra	Combretaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae Anacardiaceae Myrtaceae Meliaceae	<i>Terminalia actinophylla</i> Mart. <i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre <i>Delonix regia</i> (Hook.) Ref. <i>Mangifera indica</i> L. <i>Syzygiumcumini</i> (L.) Skeels <i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Maintenance of apiaries in the vicinity of agricultural crops, in additional providing enough harvest of honey, also results in enhanced crop yield as a consequence of higher degree of pollination.
Sahney <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh	Brassicaceae Compositae Myrtaceae Apiaceae Myrtaceae Caricaceae Rutaceae Fabaceae	<i>Brassica campestris</i> L. <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (L.) L. <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (Cartis) Skeels <i>Coriandrum sativum</i> L. <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill. <i>Carica papaya</i> L. <i>Citrus aurantiaca</i> Swingle <i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L.	<i>Brassica campestris</i> , <i>Coriandrum sativum</i> , <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> and <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> can be regarded as major bee sources of plants.
Harugade <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Vindhyaprathishthan Campus, Baramati, Pune	Meliaceae Anacardiaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss. <i>Mangifera indica</i> L. <i>Cassia fistula</i> L. <i>Cassia occidentalis</i> L. <i>Albizia amara</i> (Roxb.) B. Boiven <i>Bauhinia aculeate</i> L. <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (SW.) DC.	In order to increase honey yield and quality management of honeybee flora and floral calendar is critically important to study area.
Borkar and Mate, 2014	Chandrapur , Maharashtra	Combretaceae Anacardiaceae Asteraceae Rutaceae Fabaceae	<i>Terminalia actinophylla</i> Mart. <i>Mangifera indica</i> L. <i>Blumea adenophora</i> Franch <i>Citrus limon</i> (L.) Osbeck <i>Delonix regia</i> (Hook.) Raf.	<i>Terminalia</i> sp. constitutes the major source of pollen to the honeybees during the summer period

Tripathi, 2017	Assam, Northeast India	Fabaceae Brassicaceae Apiaceae Rhamnaceae Bombacaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae Meliaceae Fabaceae Lythraceae	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L. <i>Brassica campestris</i> L. <i>Coriandrumsativum</i> L. <i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Lam. <i>Salmaliamalabarica</i> (DC.) Schott & Endl. <i>Cassia fistula</i> L. <i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f.) Willd. <i>Toona ciliata</i> M. Roem. <i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub. <i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Roxb.	Melissopalynological investigation may contribute to and favor the possibilities of using rich flora of the studied area in order to develop beekeeping enterprises on a commercial basis, in which self-employment opportunities may be created for many disadvantaged communities in the state.
Saklani, 2017	Kangra, Himachal Pradesh	Rutaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae	<i>Citrus grandis</i> (L.) Osbeck <i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.F.) Willd. <i>Bauhinia variegata</i> L.	To create flora of multipurpose nature which will boost the beekeeping on large scale, to provide part-time or full time employment in rural areas of hilly states, to improve rural economy through enhancing the monetary and self-employment opportunities.
Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> , 2018	Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand	Rosaceae Rosaceae Rosaceae Rosaceae	<i>Prunuscerasoides</i> Buch.-Ham ex D. Don <i>Prunus persica</i> (L.) Batsch <i>Pyrus pashia</i> Buch.-Ham.ex D. Don <i>Rosa brunonii</i> Lindl	The present study is useful in the development of the analytical standard for further studies on pollen chemistry.

Dhawanet al., 2018	Newasa Tehsil, Maharashtra	Amaranthaceae Compositae Fabaceae Fabaceae Amaranthaceae Convolvulaceae Moringaceae	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex. D.C. <i>Parthenium argentatum</i> A.G ray <i>Cassia bicapsularis</i> (L.) Roxb. <i>Cassia tora</i> L. <i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre. <i>Celosia argentea</i> L. <i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	The pollen grain from honey can be used for the taxonomic identification of honey yielding plants.
Divakaran et al., 2019	Nilambar taluk, Malappuram, Kerala	Fabaceae Malvaceae Arecaceae Euphorbiaceae Cucurbitaceae Fabaceae Malvaceae Anacardiaceae Fabaceae Fabaceae Moringaceae Passifloraceae Fabaceae Sapindaceae Bignoniaceae Fabaceae Arecaceae Rubiaceae Myrtaceae	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth. <i>Bombax ceiba</i> L. <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. <i>Croton abaitensis</i> Baill. <i>Cucurbita andreana</i> Naudin <i>Delonix regia</i> (Hook.) Raf. <i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L. <i>Mangifera indica</i> L. <i>Mimosa invisia</i> Coll. <i>Mimosa pudica</i> L. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam. <i>Passiflora foetida</i> L. <i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i> (D.C.) K. Heyne <i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Merr. <i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth. <i>Vicia faba</i> L. <i>Areca catechu</i> L. <i>Ixora coccinea</i> L. <i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Increased pollen density of honey indicates the frequent visit of plants by honey bees and the more number of plant species in that area.
Krishna & Patil, 2019	Dakshin Kannada, Karnataka	Arecaceae Arecaceae Rubiaceae Fabaceae Myrtaceae	<i>Areca catechu</i> L. <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. <i>Ixora coccinea</i> L. <i>Mimosa pudica</i> L. <i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Lesser types of pollen in each honey sample indicates that their food resources are getting limited.

Layek et al., 2020	Southern West Bengal	Brassicaceae Myrtaceae Arecaceae Pedaliaceae Fabaceae Apiaceae Arecaceae Arecaceae Compositae	<i>Brassica nigra</i> (L.) K. Koch <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill. <i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L. <i>Sesamum indicum</i> L. <i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth. <i>Coriandrum sativum</i> L. <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. <i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb. <i>Mikania scandens</i> (L.) Willd.	Number of pollen foragers and the ratio of pollen foragers to total incoming foragers significantly differed according to time of day as well as season and greatly depends on resource availability.
Kumar, 2020	Eastern Dry Zone, Karnataka	Myrtaceae Arecaceae Rutaceae Euphorbiaceae Arecaceae Myrtaceae Lamiaceae Moringaceae Fabaceae	<i>Callistemon viminalis</i> (sol. ex Gaerth.) G. Don. <i>Areca catechu</i> L. <i>Citrus grandis</i> (L.) Osbeck. <i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Mull. Arg. <i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill. <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam. <i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Study will in-turn contribute to the conservation of bees, apiary development and leads to sustainable honey production.

Melissopalynological studies in India

Melissopalynological studies by different investigators in different places of India can be summed up together in a following manner:

a. Trans-Himalayan Region and Himalayan Zone

Chaturvedi (1989) and Chaudhary et al. (2018) conducted Melissopalynological studies in the Western Himalayan Region of Uttar Pradesh and Garhwal Himalaya (Uttarakhand) respectively. Their research revealed that Brassicaceae, Rosaceae, Betulaceae, and Polygonaceae are the dominant plant families in these regions. The preferred plant species for honeybees were identified as *Brassica aucheri* Boiss, *Prunus africana* (Hook. f.), *Alnus acuminata* Kunth., and *Rumex abyssinicus* Jacq. in the Western Himalayan Region of Uttar Pradesh and Garhwal Himalaya, as reported by Chaturvedi (1989). Chaudhary et al. (2018) reported Rosaceae as the dominant plant family, and the preferred plant species for honeybees in Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand were identified as *Prunus cerasoides* Buch.-Ham ex D. Don, *Prunus persica* (L.) Batsch, *Pyrus pashia* Buch.-Ham ex D. Don, and *Rosa brunonii* Lindl. In a separate study by Saklani (2017) in Himachal Pradesh, Rutaceae and Fabaceae were identified as the preferred plant species for honeybees.

b. Western Ghats, Deccan Plateau and Coastal Regions

Kalpna et al. (1990) have reported Anacardiaceae, Compositae, Arecaceae, Meliaceae, Amaranthaceae, Acanthaceae, Rubiaceae, Convolvulaceae, Zygophyllaceae, Lamiaceae, Simaroubaceae, Compositae, Fabaceae, Boraginaceae, Rutaceae, Myrtaceae, Nyctaginaceae, Rubiaceae, Malvaceae as the dominant plant families preferred by honey bees in Hyderabad. Jhansi et al. (1991, 1994) conducted similar studies in Andhra Pradesh. They have observed that Fabaceae, Combretaceae, Rutaceae, Lythraceae, Loganiaceae, Rhamnaceae, Phyllanthaceae, Meliaceae, Myrtaceae, Sapindaceae, Arecaceae, Acanthaceae, Cucurbitaceae, and Verbenaceae as dominant plant families in the region. Bhusari (2005), Laxmikant et al. (2014), Borkar et al. (2016), Borkar and Mate (2014) and Dhawan et al., (2018) have carried out extensive studies in Maharashtra region. Fabaceae, Asteraceae, Lamiaceae, Cappariaceae, Solanaceae, Combretaceae, Anacardiaceae, Myrtaceae, Meliaceae, Combretaceae, Rutaceae, Amaranthaceae,

Compositae, Convolvulaceae and Moringaceae have been reported as the dominant plant families. Krishna and Patil, (2019) and Kumar(2020) studied the Karnataka region and reported Arecaceae, Rubiaceae, Fabaceae, Myrtaceae, Rutaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Lamiaceae and Moringaceae as the dominant plant families. Divakaran et al. (2019), Sivaram (2012) and Ponnuchamy et al., (2014) studied the tropical South Indian region and reported Fabaceae, Malvaceae, Arecaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Anacardiaceae, Moringaceae, Passifloraceae, Sapindaceae, Bignoniaceae, Rubiaceae, Myrtaceae, Araliaceae and Acanthaceae as the important plant families for melissopalynological studies. Harugade et al.(2016) reported Meliaceae, Anacardiaceae and Fabaceae as preferred plant families for melissopalynological studies.

c. Gangetic Plains

Chaturvedi (2009) and Chauhan et al.(2013) studied Lucknow region for melissopalynological studies. They have reported Fabaceae, Xanthorrhoeaceae, Amaranthaceae, Rosaceae, Compositae, Rutaceae, Linaceae, Meliaceae, Arecaceae, Myrtaceae, Sapotaceae, Moringaceae, Moraceae, Menispermaceae as the preferred plant families by honey bees. Datta et al.(2008) reported Brassicaceae, Apiaceae, Myrtaceae, Polygonaceae and Asteraceae as the preferred plantfamilies in the Upper Gangetic Region. Sahney et al.(2016) studied the Varanasi region and reported Brassicaceae, Compositae, Myrtaceae, Apiaceae, Caricaceae, Rutaceae and Fabaceae as the important plant family for nectar collection by the bees. Bhattacharya (2014) and Layek(2020) reported Brassicaceae, Myrtaceae, Arecaceae, Pedaliaceae, Fabaceae, Apiaceae and Compositae as the important plant families for melissopalynological studies in West Bengal region.

d. North-East Region

Tripathi (2017) undertook melissopalynological studies in Assam and reported Fabaceae, Brassicaceae, Apiaceae, Rhamnaceae, Bombacaceae, Meliaceae and Lythraceae as the important plant families for collection of pollen by bees.

Current status and future prospects:

Melissopalynological studies in India have been conducted by various scientific groups since the early 1990s, contributing significantly to our understanding of bee foraging plant families in different states and seasons. These studies have played a crucial role in advancing apicultural knowledge. However, there are still gaps in the data, particularly in certain biogeographic zones of the country and the analysis of physicochemical components of honey. Addressing these gaps is necessary to further enhance the Indian apicultural market and establish a scientifically controlled honey market in the country.

To achieve these goals, it is essential to develop a comprehensive dataset adhering to internationally recommended standards for honey. This standardized data can greatly contribute to the advancement of apiculture knowledge and facilitate the growth of the Indian apicultural industry. By meticulously collecting and analyzing data on various aspects of honey production, including plant species, geographical locations, and physicochemical properties, researchers can establish a robust foundation for the apicultural sector in India.

Such a thorough and standardized dataset will provide valuable insights into the diverse bee foraging plant families across different regions and seasons. It will enable beekeepers and stakeholders to make informed decisions about beekeeping practices, honey production, and marketing strategies. Moreover, this wealth of information will foster collaborations between scientists, beekeepers, and policymakers, driving innovation and sustainable development in the apicultural sector.

In conclusion, building a comprehensive and internationally recognized database of honey production standards is essential for the growth of the Indian apicultural market. By addressing the existing data gaps and following recommended standards, India can enhance its apicultural knowledge, improve the quality of honey produced, and foster the development of a scientifically regulated honey market.

REFERENCES:

1. Zumla, A., &Lulat, A. (1990). Honey - A remedy rediscovered. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 83(2), 127.
2. Manyi-Loh, C. E., Clarke, A. M., & N dip, R. N. (2011). An overview of honey: Therapeutic properties and contribution in nutrition and human health. *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, 5(8), 844–852. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ajmr10.008>
3. Bibi, S., Husain, S. Z., & Malik, R. N. (2008). Pollen analysis and heavy metals detection in honey samples from seven selected countries. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 40(2), 507–516
4. Paredes, R., & Bryant, V. M. (2020). Pollen analysis of honey samples from the Peruvian Amazon. *Palynology*, 44(2), 344–354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01916122.2019.1604447>
5. Bryant, V. M. (2001). the R-Values of Honey: Pollen Coefficients. *Palynology*, 25(1), 11–28. <https://doi.org/10.2113/0250011>
6. Chauhan, M. S., Farooqui, A., & Trivedi, A. (2017). Plants foraged by bees for honey production in northern India: The diverse flora of India and its implications for apiculture. *ActaPalaeobotanica*, 57(1), 119–132. <https://doi.org/10.1515/acpa-2017-0003>
7. Chaturvedi, M. (1989). Pollen analysis of some spring honeys from the western Himalayan region of Uttar Pradesh, India. In *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Plant Sci)* (Vol. 99).
8. Chauhan, M. S., Trivedi, A., & Sharma, A. (2013). Pollen analysis of multifloral honey from Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India. *Phytomorphology: An International Journal of Plant Morphology*, 63(3–4), 133–141.
9. Chauhan, M. S., & Trivedi, A. (2011). Pollen analysis of honey from Lucknow District, Uttar Pradesh. In *J. Appl. Biosci* (Vol. 37).
10. Kalpana, T. P., Fatima, K., &Ramanujam, C. G. K. (1990). Pollen analysis of Apis cerana and Apisflorea honeys from Adikmet area, Hyderabad. In *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Plant Sci.)* (Vol. 100).
11. Jhansi, P., Kalpana; C, T. P., &Ramanujam, G. K. (1991). Pollen analysis of rock bee summer honeys from the Prakasam district of the Andhra Pradesh, India. In *Journal of Apicultura/ Research* (Vol. 30).

12. Jhansi, P., Kalpana, T. P., &Ramanujam, C. (1994). Pollen analysis of some *Apis ceranaFabr* honeys from Andhra Pradesh, India.
13. Balachandra, C., D, S. C. M., & Ramachandra, T. V. (1999). Honeybee Diversity , Role in Pollination and Beekeeping Scenario in South Indian Western Ghats.
14. Singh, M. . (1999). Melissopalynology and Survey of the Bee Plants in North-Eastern Hill Region.pdf. Indian J Hill Farmg, 79–83.
15. Sivaram, V. (2001). Honeybee flora and beekeeping in Karnataka State, India. Proc. 37th Int. Apic. Congr., 28 Oct – 1 Nov 2001, Durban, South Africa, (080).
16. Bhusari, N. V., Mate, D. M., &Makde, K. H. (2005). Pollen of Apis honey from Maharashtra. Grana, 44(3), 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00173130510010585>
17. Datta, K., Verma, P. C., & Chatterjee, A. (2008). Mapping of key bee flora of upper Gangetic region of India - A palynological assessment through regional honeys. Grana, 47(2), 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00173130801980109>
18. Sivaram, V; Roopa, P; Shubharani, R; Suwannapong, G. (2012). Pollen Analysis in Honeys Collected from Karnataka Region of NilgiriBiosphere , South India. Journal of Apiculture, 27(3), 223–231.
19. Bhusari, N. V., Mate, D. M., &Makde, K. H. (2005). Pollen of Apis honey from Maharashtra. Grana, 44(3), 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00173130510010585>
20. Bhattacharya, A. (2014). RESEARCH ARTICLE MELISSOPALYNOLOGICAL STUDY OF NADIA DISTRICT , WEST BENGAL , INDIA * Ashoke Bhattacharya.
21. Ponnuchamy, R., Bonhomme, V., Prasad, S., Das, L., Patel, P., Gaucherel, C., ... Anupama, K. (2014). Honey pollen: Using melissopalynology to understand foraging preferences of bees in tropical south India. PLoS ONE, 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0101618>
22. Laxmikant, B., & Devendra, M. (2014). Summer Pollen Sources to Apis dorsata honey bees collected from Bramhapuri forest area of Chandrapur District of Maharashtra State (India). 2(2), 160–164.
23. Borkar, L., & Mate, D. (2016). Melittopalynological Study of Squeezed Summer Honeys Collected from Forest Area of SindewahiTahsil of Chandrapur District, (Maharashtra state). International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), 5(6), 2053–2060. <https://doi.org/10.21275/v5i6.nov164804>
24. Sahney, M., Kumar, A., &Rahi, S. (2016). Pollen Analysis of Honeys from Varanasi District , Uttar Pradesh , India. Biological Forum – An International Journal, 8(March 2014), 126–133.
25. Harugade, S., Gawate, A. B., Shinde, B., & District, P. (2016). Bee Floral Diversity of Medicinal Plants in VidyaPratishthanCampus ,. 5(11), 425–431.
26. Laxmikant, Borkar; Devendra, M. (2014). Melittopalynological Investigation of winter honeys collected from Apis dorsata hives of Multahsil of Chandrapur District of Maharashtra State (India). International Research Journal of Science & Engineering, 2(3), 112–118.
27. Tripathi, S., Basumatary, S. K., Bera, S. K., Brahma, M., & Sarma, G. C. (2017). A palynological study of natural honeys from the Bongaigaon district of Assam, northeast India. Palynology, 41(3), 389–400. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01916122.2016.1217950>
28. Saklani, S., &Mattu, V. K. (2017). Melissopalynological investigations on honey samples of Kangra hills, Himachal Pradesh, India. International Journal of Entomology Research, (July 2017), 41–51. Retrieved from www.entomologyjournals.com
29. Chaudhary, E., Tiwari, P., &Uniyal, P. L. (2018). Morphology and pollen chemistry of several bee forage taxa of family rosaceae from garhwalhimalaya, uttarakhand, india. Journal of Apicultural Science, 62(2), 167–177. <https://doi.org/10.2478/JAS-2018-0015>
30. Dhawan, A. S., Pawar, K. W., &Lokhande, A. A. (2018). Analysis of pollen grains in different honey samples from the region of Newasa tehsil in Maharashtra. Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, 7(3), 3438–3442.
31. Divakaran, A. N., Joseph, S., & Nadu, T. (2019). Melissopalynological analysis of honey samples collected from Nilambur Taluk in Malappuram district , Kerala. 20–22.
32. Krishna, A. G. S., &Patil, R. K. (2019). Foraging preferences of honey bees Apiscerana in Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka, India. Journal of Threatened Taxa, 11(6), 13756–13764. <https://doi.org/10.11609/jott.4265.11.6.13756-13764>
33. Layek, U., Manna, S. S., &Karmakar, P. (2020). Pollen foraging behaviour of honey bee (*Apis mellifera* L.) in southern West Bengal, India. Palynology, 44(1), 114–126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01916122.2018.1533898>
34. Kumar, V. (2020). The melissopalynological investigation in the Eastern Dry Zone of Karnataka, India. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.07.06.189274>